

REPLICATION PROCESS OF STUDY

This document is complementary material used to evaluate the snowballing performance varying the seed set creation under the diversity perspective from the proposed tool. Specifically, the document is divided into three parts: 1) General information; 2) *Repository Organization*; 3) *Replication Process of Study*.

1. General Information

- For replication of our study titled “Assessing diversity in creating seed set for snowballing search for systematic literature review in software engineering” we used as base the following SLRs:
 - “*Knowledge Management in Software Testing: A Systematic Snowball Literature Review*” named in our study as Original SLR1.
 - “*Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review*”, named in our study as Original SLR2.
- We used the SLR1 e SLR2 *for the snowballing replication*.
- The study proposes one research question to evaluate the performance of snowballing in terms of recall, precision *and F-measure using a the proposed approach*.

2. Repository Organization

- **Seed Set SLRs:** Contains the papers used as seed set on the Original *SLR1 and SLR2*; and *the proposed approach operationalized by the tool for SLR1 and SLR2*.
- **SLR1 - Snowballing Replication Data:** Contains the results of the *execution snowballing using the seed sets generated by the proposed approach for the SLR1*
- **SLR2 - Snowballing Replication Data:** Contains the results of the *execution snowballing using the seed sets generated by the proposed approach for the SLR2*

3. Replication Process of Study

Two steps must be performed to replicate the study: 1) using the tool to generate seed sets; 2) executing the snowballing process.

- *Seed set recommendation tool can be accessed at:* <https://seed-set-recommendation.onrender.com/>

3.1. Using the tool for SLR1

This section illustrates the use of tool steps for SLR1.

1) Enter Your Research Question (RQ):

- a. Start by entering your research question into the tool's interface.

RQ utilized: Which software testing aspects and techniques receive more attention when applying Knowledge Management?

2) Extract Keywords:

- a. Click on 'Extract Keywords' to identify the main concepts related to your RQ.
- b. You can edit the Extracted Keywords to remove words that are not necessary.

Keywords utilized: Software testing, Knowledge *management*.

3) Add Synonyms:

- a. Optionally, add synonyms for each Extracted Keyword to refine the search criteria.

Synonyms utilized:

- **Synonyms for "Software testing":** Software test

- **Synonyms for "Knowledge Management":** KM, Tacit knowledge, Explicit knowledge, Knowledge creation, Knowledge acquisition, Knowledge sharing, Knowledge retention, Knowledge valuation, Knowledge use, Knowledge discovery, Knowledge Integration, Knowledge theory, Knowledge, Knowledge engineering, Experience transfer, Technology transfer

4) Generate Search String:

- a. Click on 'Generate Search String' to create the search string based on the Extracted Keywords and synonyms.
- b. You can edit the Generated Search String if needed.

- String utilized:

("Software testing" OR "Software test") AND ("Knowledge management" OR KM OR "Tacit knowledge" OR "Explicit knowledge" OR "Knowledge creation" OR "Knowledge acquisition" OR "Knowledge sharing" OR "Knowledge retention" OR "Knowledge valuation" OR "Knowledge use" OR "Knowledge discovery" OR "Knowledge Integration" OR "Knowledge theory" OR Knowledge OR "Knowledge engineering" OR "Experience transfer" OR "Technology transfer")

5) Set Search Years (Optional):

- a. If desired, enter the start and end years for the search to narrow down the results.
- b. Year: 2003 to 2015

6) View Search Results:

- a. Click on “Results from Scopus” to open a new tab displaying all the articles returned in the search.

7) Generate Seed Set:

- a. Click on “Generate seed set” to view the seed set recommended by the tool.

3.2. Snowballing Process for SLR1

Use the downloaded papers and seed set recommendations to replicate the study's methodology and evaluate the performance of snowballing. The articles used in the snowballing process are presented in the file named “Snowballing analysis”. The snowballing process was conducted into three steps:

- 1) Identification of the Seed Set in the SLR Original**
- 2) Conduction of snowballing backward and forward using the seed set generated by tool in the Step 3.1**
- 3) Analysis of snowballing results**